

Household Hand-Hygiene Audit CRF

#	Question	Variable
1	Today's date	DD/MM/YYYY
2	Household ID	
Section 1: Exited Household members		
3	Time of event being observed	MM:HH
4	Person being observed	Mother Father Grand parent Child Relation Visitor Nanny
5	Event being observed	After toilet Before food prep Before child feeding Before eating Changing nappy After cleaning Touching animals Touch dirty things Other (specify)
6	Specify event being observed (detail notes)	
7	Handwashing action	No Action Water only Water with soap Water with ash Water with sand Water with flour
8	Handwashing facility	Piped to tap Tippy tap Jug and basin Bucket without tap Bucket with tap Cup only Dipped in communal container Dipped in container Other (specify)

9	Handwashing facility location	Next to latrine Under dish rack In HH yard Inside the house HH well Other (specify)
10	Comments (detailed notes)	
11	<i>You have completed data collection for this event. Please record all future events on separate forms</i>	
12	Staff signature	
13	Time and Date	MM:HH DD/MM/YYYY